

UV spectrophotometric method for simultaneous estimation of tizanidine and valdecoxib in tablet dosage forms

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Abstract : The simple, selective, rapid and precise UV spectrophotometric method has been developed for the simultaneous estimation of valdecoxib and tizanidine in pharmaceutical dosage form. The proposed method is based on the Vierordt's simultaneous equations. Tizanidine has absorption maxima at 318.1 nm and valdecoxib absorption maxima at 239.0 nm in methanol. The linearity was observed in the concentration range of 2–18 µg/ml for tizanidine and valdecoxib. Both the drugs obey Beer's law. The method is validated statistically. The recovery studies confirmed the accuracy of the proposed method.

Keywords : Simultaneous equations, tizanidine, valdecoxib, absorptivity coefficient.

Introduction

Valdecoxib, a new cox-2 inhibitor, an anti-inflammatory drug is 4,5-(5-methyl-3-phenylisoxazol-4-yl)benzene sulfonamide¹. It is yet not official in any pharmacopoeia. Tizanidine is a muscle relaxant official in Martindale². Chemically it is 5-chloro-N-(2-imidazolin-2-yl)-2,1,3-benzothiadiazol-4-yl amine hydrochloride. Both the drugs in combination are used in the treatment of painful muscle spasm and disc prolapsed. Literature reveals that various methods have been developed for the determination of tizanidine alone as well as when in combination with valdecoxib and other drugs^{3–9}. The aim of this paper was to explore the possibility of using the Vierordt's simulta-

neous equation method^{10,11} for the simultaneous estimation of valdecoxib and tizanidine in tablet dosage forms.

Results and discussion

In proposed method, two wavelengths were used for the analysis of drugs 318.1 nm (λ_{\max} of tizanidine) and 239.0 nm (λ_{\max} of valdecoxib). The optical characteristics such as Beer's law limit (µg/ml), correlation co-efficient, slope (*m*), y-intercept, molar absorptivity (L/mol cm⁻¹) and Sandell's sensitivity (µg/cm²/0.001) were calculated for the method and the results are summarised in Table 1. The analysis results of marketed formulation were in good agreement with their labelled claim. The

Table 1. Optical characteristics

Parameters	318.1 nm		239.0 nm	
	Valdecoxib	Tizanidine	Valdecoxib	Tizanidine
Beer's law limit (µg/ml)	-	2–18	2–18	2–18
Molar absorptivity (L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹) ^a	-	7.719 × 10 ³	2.018 × 10 ⁴	9.402 × 10 ³
Sandell's sensitivity (µg cm ² /0.001 absorbance unit) ^a	-	0.0375	0.0155	0.0308
Regression equation		$Y = mx + c$		
Slope (<i>m</i>)	0.0288	0.0589	0.0286	
Intercept ^o	-0.0163	0.044	0.029	
Correction coefficient ^o	0.9965	0.9981	0.9974	

^aAverage of nine determinations.

recovery ranged between 98 to 100% for tested formulation (T-1, T-2). The proposed method was simple, sensitive, accurate and precise and can be successfully applied in estimation of tizanidine and valdecoxib in tablet dosage forms. Results of analysis of tablets are shown in Table 2. No interference from the excipients was confirmed by performing the recovery experiment for which standard addition method was employed. The recovery of added standard was found at four different concentra-

Table 2. Average weight of tablets

Tablet	Average weight (g)	
	Before removing coating	After removing coating
T-1	0.3206	0.2978
T-2	0.3143	0.3228

tion levels for each drug. From the total amount of drug, the percentage recovery was calculated. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity values show the sensitivity of both the drugs at both the wavelengths. The precision is confirmed by percentage RSD. The reproducibility, repeatability and accuracy of these methods were found to be good as evidenced by low standard deviation. The proposed method can be successfully applied for the estimation of valdecoxib and tizanidine in combined dosage form.

Experimental

Reagents and chemicals : Methanol was procured from Spectrochem Pvt. Ltd. while acetone, acetonitrile, ethanol, *n*-octanol were procured from Qualigens fine chemicals, Mumbai. All the chemicals used were of analytical grade. Tizanidine and valdecoxib supplied by Sun Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd., Gujarat and Ipca Laboratories Ltd., Ratlam respectively as gift samples.

Instruments : A double beam GBC Cintra-10, UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Australia) with 1 cm matched cuvettes was used for all spectral measurements.

Methods : Vierod't (simultaneous equation method)^{10,11} was used for the simultaneous estimation of valdecoxib and tizanidine in tablet dosage forms with validation study later¹². Tizanidine (100 mg) and valdecoxib (100 mg) were weighed accurately and dissolved in 100 ml methanol to give stock solution of 1000 µg/ml concentration. From these stock solutions, working standard solutions of drugs (100 µg/ml) were prepared by appropriate dilutions. Working standard solutions were scanned in the

entire UV range (200–400 nm) to determine the λ_{\max} of the particular drug. The λ_{\max} of tizanidine and valdecoxib were found to be 318.1 nm and 239.0 nm respectively. The standard solutions were prepared having concentrations 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18 µg/ml for tizanidine and valdecoxib using the working standard solution. The absorbances of these standard solutions were measured at 318.1 nm and 239.0 nm and calibration curves were plotted at these wavelengths. The absorptivity coefficients of these two drugs were determined using calibration curve. Two simultaneous equations were formed using these absorptivity coefficient values.

$$A_1 = 0.0266 C_2 \quad (1)$$

$$A_2 = -0.0642 C_1 + 0.0324 C_2 \quad (2)$$

where C1 and C2 are the concentrations of valdecoxib and tizanidine respectively in g/ml in the sample solution. A1 and A2 are the absorbances of the mixture at 318.1 nm and 239.0 nm respectively. The synthetic mixture of the combination of both the drugs were prepared in the ratio of 1 : 5 (tizanidine : valdecoxib). The ratio of drugs in the synthetic mixture was based upon the dosage strength of formulation in combination, which is available in the market. Now the absorbance of the synthetic mixtures was measured at two wavelengths and the concentrations of valdecoxib and tizanidine were calculated.

Procedure of the analysis of tablet : Twenty tablets of same respective batch numbers of two pharmaceutical companies were taken. The IP method was followed to determine the average weight (before and after removing the coating). These tablets were then finely powdered and triturated well. A quantity of powder equivalent to 10 mg of tizanidine and 50 mg of valdecoxib were transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask and mixed with methanol (50 ml) and sonicated for 15 min and the volume was made upto 100 ml. The solution was filtered through Whatmann filter paper No. 40. From the filtrate 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3 ml solutions were pipette out separately and diluted to mark with methanol in 10 ml volumetric flask. The absorbances of these solutions were measured at 318.1 nm and 239.0 nm using methanol as blank. Concentrations of two drugs in the sample solution were determined using eqs. (1) and (2).

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